

ECONOMIC IMPORTANCE OF THE COUNTRY'S STOCK MARKET**Abbazov Abdulaziz Shavkat ugli**

Student of Tashkent State University of Economics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10902217>

This thesis comprehensively examines the role of the stock market in economic development and stability, studies their economic importance and decisive role in the distribution of capital, economic growth, and financial stability.

The term stock market refers to exchanges where shares of public companies are bought and sold. Such financial activities are carried out through official exchanges and over-the-counter markets that operate based on a set of rules. The terms "stock market" and "stock exchange" are often used interchangeably. Stock traders buy or sell stocks on one or more stock exchanges that are part of the general stock market.

The value of global domestic equity market increased from 65.04 trillion U.S. dollars in 2013 to 98.5 trillion U.S. dollars in 2022. As of July 2023, the total market capitalization of domestic companies listed on stock exchanges worldwide recorded as 112 trillion U.S. dollars.

Figure 1. Total capitalization of stock markets worldwide

These numbers mean that year after year, by attracting the growing demand for stock markets, the country can accelerate its economic development, or in other words, increase the flow of investments into the country and thereby increase the country's economic growth rates.

The stock market is an integral part of market relations. At a time when the development of the productive forces of society requires a revision of the

attitude to the stock market, the relevance of this area is increasing, because it is the stock that in many ways increases the efficiency of the movement of return of value, changes in the form of ownership, is the key to solving the problems of transfer to private ownership.

Since 2018, an electronic system for the sale of state assets through electronic trading platforms has been established in our country. In 2018, the banking system began to focus on the issues of ensuring effective and mutually beneficial cooperation between banks and business entities in the implementation of the tasks set for the development of the banking system. Despite the hesitancy and advice of some experts who are against the reform of the currency market, we have started the process of currency liberalization based on international standards in a short period of time. Currency policy should fully serve the interests of business and economic development and give a positive impetus to investment activity. In the process of globalization, if the economic sector forms the basis of the country's development, the financial market is also the basis of economic development. Currently, digitalization is being paid a lot of attention and is the main goal, and all operations and functions of the stock market are carried out in an open manner.

The economic significance of stock markets can be distilled into several key functions they perform within a country's economy:

1. Capital Formation: Stock markets provide a platform for companies to raise capital by issuing shares of stock. This process is critical for businesses looking to expand, invest in new projects, or improve infrastructure.

2. Investment Opportunities: They offer a variety of investment opportunities for individual and institutional investors, facilitating the allocation of financial resources to the most promising economic sectors.

3. Corporate Governance: Publicly listed companies are typically subject to stringent reporting requirements and oversight, which can lead to improved corporate governance and management practices.

4. Risk Diversification: Stock markets allow investors to diversify their portfolios across different sectors and assets, spreading risk and reducing the impact of any single economic event.

5. Economic Indicators: Stock market indices often serve as indicators of the economic health of a country, with rising markets indicating positive investor sentiment and economic growth, and vice versa.

6. Global Capital Allocation: They facilitate the flow of capital across borders, allowing for international investment and economic integration.

7. Innovation and Entrepreneurship: A vibrant stock market can stimulate innovation and entrepreneurship by enabling access to capital for new, high-growth-potential firms.

The performance of stock markets can be influenced by a range of factors, including economic policies, political stability, regulatory environment, global economic conditions, and market sentiment. A robust and well-regulated stock market is often seen as a cornerstone of a healthy economy because it supports growth and fosters confidence among investors.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the improvement of the financial market is the basis of the country's economic development. On the one hand, the state economy will benefit to a certain extent, and on the other hand, the population will benefit by rationally directing idle funds. To develop the country's financial market, it is necessary to further develop the level of financial liquidity, as well as the primary and secondary financial market systems. Also, it is necessary to increase the investment activity of the financial market, including the increase in the value of assets and trading volumes, and it is necessary to ensure the activity of all participants of the securities market. The development of the stock market is considered appropriate for the activation of financial resources, their rational use and redistribution to accelerate economic development. This is the basis of the country's economic development.

References:

1. Khamidov Bekzodjon, Razzoqov Jasur, Prospective directions of financial market development in Uzbekistan, TMI 2023
2. Akramjon Karimov, Economic mechanisms of ensuring the activity of investors in the development of the stock market, Scientific Journal of "International Finance & Accounting" Issue 4, August 2023. ISSN: 2181-1016
3. Stock Markets: A Spur to Economic Growth, Ross Levine, Finance & Development, March 1996
4. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Address of M. Mirziyoyev on the conclusion of the main works carried out in 2017 and the most priority directions of socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018
5. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/274490/global-value-of-share-holdings-since-2000/>
6. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/stockmarket.asp>
7. Kubayevich, K. F. (2024). Current Analysis and Current Issues of Ensuring the Financial Stability of the Banking System in Uzbekistan. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY, 4(3), 169-176.

8. Javlon, Baxronov, and G'aniyev Shahridin. "DAVLAT SEKTORIDA ICHKI AUDITNING XORIY TAJRIBASI." UNIVERSAL JOURNAL OF TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATION 1.8 (2023): 29-38.
9. Murtazaevich K. S. Improving Foreign Investment Insurance in Uzbekistan //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2023. – Т. 20. – С. 68-79.
10. Холмаматов Ф. К. ТИЖОРАТ БАНКЛАРИДА ЛИКВИДЛИЛИК РИСКНИ БОШҚАРИШ АМАЛИЁТИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ МОЛИЯВИЙ БАРҚАРОРЛИГИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШ: Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari //Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. – 2024. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 375-382.
11. Murtazaevich K. S., Vohidovich G. S. ISSUES OF INCREASING THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF THE INVESTMENT CLIMATE WHEN ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS INTO THE ECONOMY. – 2024.
12. Сулейманов, И. ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЕ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ НА БАНКОВСКИЙ И РЕАЛЬНЫЙ СЕКТОРА ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЕО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ НЕСТАБИЛЬНОСТИ.
13. Aminova N. XORIYIY INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB QILISH ORQALI O 'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH //Ўзбекистон республикаси суғурта бозори учун кадрлар тайёрлашнинг ҳозирга ҳолати, муаммолари ва ривожланиш истиқболлари. – С. 132.
14. Сулейманов И. Пути усиления интеграции банковского и реального секторов экономики: Монография / И. Сулейманов; –Т.: "Iqtisod-Moliya", 2024. 112 с.
15. Kiyosov S. U. et al. WAYS TO ENSURE THE STABILITY OF STATE FINANCES BY INCREASING LOCAL BUDGET REVENUES //Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 21-26.
16. Suleymanov, I. (2024). FEATURES OF FINANCIAL SUPPORT FOR THE REAL SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF GEO-FINANCIAL POLICY INSTABILITY. Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development, 23, 33-43.
17. Asqar, C., & Farhod, X. (2022). The profitability indicators of commercial banks in the republic of Uzbekistan and their modern state. World Economics and Finance Bulletin, 8, 141-148.

18. Suleymanov, I. (2024). CHALLENGES IN ENHANCING THE RESOURCE FOUNDATION OF COMMERCIAL BANKS THROUGH THE INTEGRATION OF BANKING SYSTEMS WITH THE REAL ECONOMY SECTOR.